

To Study Of Self-Confidence Of Students In Nss And Non Nss

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Abstract:

The study was conducted to assess the self-confidence of students in NSS and non NSS in senior college. The sample consisted of total 60 students, 30 students in NSS (15 boys & 15 Girls) and 30 students in non NSS (15 boys & 15 Girls) were selected from S.S.C. College, Junnar. Simple random sampling method for used for data collection. For this study self-confidence Inventory for Dr. M. Basavanna was used to assess the self-confidence of the selected respondent. Mean, SD, 't' value etc. statistics techniques were used for data analysis and interpreting. The findings were no significant difference of self-confidence of students in NSS and non NSS, no significant difference of self-confidence of boys in NSS and non NSS and no significant difference of self-confidence of girls in NSS and non NSS. This means, the self-confidence of Students, boys and girls in NSS and non NSS are similar.

Introduction:

The National Service Scheme NSS, is a major youth activity intended to engage the university and college students in social service on a voluntary basis. The history of NSS dates back to the post independence days of India. The University Grants Commission headed by Dr. Radhakrishnan recommended introduction of national service in the academic institutions on a voluntary basis for developing healthy contacts between the students and teachers on the one hand. NSS programme have expanded both quantitatively and qualitatively. The watchword of the National Service Scheme is 'NOT ME BUT YOU'. In these days of mass social decadence it can be said that in college life a student can develop his moral values through the NSS. This reflects the essence of democratic living and upholds the need for selfless service. It underlines that the welfare of an individual ultimately depends on the welfare of society on the whole.

Self-confidence:

Basavanna (1971), "Self confidence is a phenomenological construct and no chain is stronger than its weakest link is an unequivocal truth in the field of characters."

Good (1973), "Self confidence is a faith in one's own ability." A self confidence person is defined as one who perceived himself as socially competent, emotionally mature, intellectually adequate, successful, satisfied, decisive, optimistic, independent, selfreliant, self-assure, straightforward, fairly assertive, having leadership qualifies and in general as having positive and constructive self feeling evaluation.

Self confidence is considered one of the most influential motivators and regulators of behavior in people's everyday lives. A growing body of evidence suggests that one's perception of ability or self confidence is the central mediating construct of achievement strivings. Self confidence is not a motivational perspective by itself. It is a judgment

about capabilities for accomplishment of some goal, and therefore, must be considered within a broader conceptualization of motivation that provides the goal context.

Methods of Building Self-Confidence:

1. Communicating with Yourself: Communicating with your self is the primary way to build self-confidence.
2. Accepting Responsibility: Everyone should welcome opportunity without thinking of success or failure.
3. Awareness of Abilities: Individuals have a variety of latent abilities.
4. Goal Seating: Your goal is not just to have a resolution but to set according to your ability.
5. Positive Attitude: A positive attitude is one of the most important factor in fulfilling your aspirations.
6. Reactions of Others: Presenting one's goals, feelings, experience, needs, thoughts to experts and taking a positive view of others reactions helps one to recognize one's abilities and build one's self-confidence.

Rationale of study:

The students participating in NSS do voluntary and selfless community service. Shyness and fear are not seen in these students while doing this work. Does this make these students more self-confident than non NSS students? This topic has been chosen for the purpose of getting the attention this factor and grow in it and progress themselves..

Objective of Study:

1. To study the self-confidence of students in NSS and non NSS.
2. To study the self-confidence of boys in NSS and non NSS.
3. To study the self-confidence of girls in NSS and non NSS.

Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant difference in the self-confidence of students in NSS and non NSS.

2. There is no significant difference in the self-confidence of boys in NSS and non NSS.

3. There is no significant difference in the self-confidence of girls in NSS and non NSS.

Method:

1. Sample: In this study, researcher has select total 60 students in senior college, 30 students in NSS (15 boys & 15 Girls) and 30 students in non NSS (15 boys & 15 Girls). Sample was select from S.S.C.College, Junnar through simple random sampling method for used for data collection. The participants was arts, commerce and science faculty undergraduate students.

2. Variable: Independent Variable:- NSS and non NSS students.

3. Dependent Variable:- Self-Confidence

4. Research Tools: The Self Confidence Inventory developed by Dr. M. Basavanna. This inventory was designed for adolescents and adults. The Inventory has a total of 100 statements. Every statement has two alternative answers 'true' and 'false'. Low Score indicate to high level of self confidence. The reliability Coefficient, as corrected by Spearman Brown Prophecy Formula, was found to be 0.94, and validity coefficient was 0.76.

5. Statistical Analysis:

In the present research Mean, SD, 't' value etc. Statistical techniques were used for the data analysis and interpretation.

Result & Discussion:

Table No. 1 showing the significant difference in self-confidence of students in NSS and non NSS.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Self-Confidence	NSS Students	62.5	10.95	30	0.80	NS
	Non NSS Students	63.05	10.29	30		

The table no. 1 it is shows that, the NSS Students mean value is 62.5 and standard deviation value is 10.95. Like the non NSS students mean value is 63.05 and standard deviation value is 10.29. The non NSS students mean value is more than NSS students. Obtained 't' value of the difference

between the mean of these two groups was found to be 0.80. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference in self-confidence of students in NSS and non NSS.

Table No. 2 showing the significant difference in self-confidence of boys in NSS and non NSS.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Self-Confidence	NSS boys	61.5	6.32	15	0.49	NS
	Non NSS boys	62.83	8.39	15		

The table no. 2 it is shows that, the NSS boys mean value is 61.5 and standard deviation value is 6.32. Like the non NSS boys mean value is 62.83 and standard deviation value is 8.39. The non NSS boys mean value is more than NSS boys. Obtained 't' value of the difference between the mean of these

two groups was found to be 0.49. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference of self-confidence of boys in boys in NSS and non NSS.

Table No. 3 showing the significant difference in self-confidence of girls in NSS and non NSS.

Variable	Type	Mean	SD	N	't'	Sign.
Self-Confidence	NSS Girls	63.5	6.32	15	0.74	NS
	Non NSS Girls	61.5	8.19	15		

The table no. 3 it is shows that, the NSS girls mean value is 63.5 and standard deviation value is 6.32. Like the non NSS girls mean value is 61.5 and standard deviation value is 8.19. The NSS girls mean value is more than non NSS girls. Obtained 't' value of the difference between the mean of these two groups was found to be 0.74. This is no significant at 0.05 levels. So the null hypothesis was accepted. That is, there was a no significant difference of self-confidence of girls in NSS and non NSS.

and non NSS and no significant difference of self-confidence of girls in NSS and non NSS. This means, the self-confidence of students, boys and girls in NSS and non NSS are similar.

Suggestions:

- 1) A large number of samples can be taken in future research.
- 2) The study area for further research will come from a wide area.
- 3) Various techniques should be used to analyze the scores.

Conclusion:

There is no significant difference of self-confidence of students in NSS and non NSS, no significant difference of self-confidence of boys in NSS

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